

Academic Guidelines and Recommendations for Integrating Green Coding Aspects into Curricula of Higher Education

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Supplementary Material A – Full Transcript of the Academic Workshop on Integrating Green Coding into Curricula of Higher Education on EnviroInfo23

The Academic Workshop took place on Wednesday, October 11th, as part of the Special Track I of EnviroInfo23 at Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) Garching³. The workshop was announced as German Speaking with the following description:” The workshop investigates the integration of technology and sustainability, focusing on incorporating green coding into curricula. It explores challenges, opportunities, and potential implementations. The workshop comprises in-depth discussions about initial efforts to introduce green coding through a course at HTW Berlin titled “Design and Implementation of a Lecture teaching Current Green Coding Approaches and Practices at HTW Berlin,” offering foundational insights. Additionally, a presentation on integrating green coding into existing study programs provides practical applications. Participants are encouraged to share experiences and insights into integrating green coding into curricula, with qualitative inputs analyzed for a comprehensive understanding. Outcomes will shape academic guidelines for broader dissemination. Join this transformative platform shaping the future of tech education, uniting sustainability and technology through green coding. It welcomes researchers, educators, and curriculum developers passionate about sustainable tech education, valuing your contributions to the discourse on green coding’s educational impact.”

Question 1: Does it make more sense for you to incorporate green coding content into stand-alone modules/teaching units or to add green coding aspects to existing modules?

Experts uniformly agree that it is preferable to incorporate green coding information into education in various contexts rather than limiting it to stand-alone modules or teaching units. They suggest that this technique addresses the issue of green coding awareness and assures accessibility to the subject matter. Furthermore, the experts recommend incorporating sustainability principles into standard computer science courses, citing the University of Würzburg’s Computer Science and Sustainability course as an example of an established foundational understanding. They also argue for developing a specific course focusing on sustainability fundamentals as a necessary component of education in this profession. The experts analyzed the advantages of integrating green coding material inside modules or teaching units. The researchers emphasized students’ inclination, namely those pursuing type 2 computer science courses, towards green coding content and broadening green coding to disciplines beyond computer science degrees, e.g., type 0 courses. They also observed that instructors frequently neglect the inclusion of green coding information in their curriculum, resulting in a relative deficiency of green coding-related issues in computer science education. The specialist from the University of Applied Science, Bochum, emphasized utilizing customized green coding material to cater to specific requirements, demonstrating a dedication to digital sustainability and the imperative for individualized methods to green coding integration. The participants argued for the utilization of degree programs to promote greater incorporation of green coding material, as they can yield a more substantial influence than individual courses. The “Gesellschaft für Informatik e. V.” acknowledgment was regarded as a significant milestone in facilitating the further integration of green coding material. The experts advocated for implementing programs to increase knowledge regarding the significance of green coding content. Furthermore, one expert underscored the necessity of adopting a well-rounded strategy that guarantees a thorough examination of green coding content. The importance of customization was also highlighted, as the expert-recommended incorporating green coding content into specialist subjects to facilitate personalized integration on a field-specific level. The logical development of extending the scope of green coding education to schools is advocated by the expert who proposes the inclusion of GI in computer science education at the school level. The participants emphasized the importance of extending from traditional energy-efficient algorithm techniques as a crucial aspect in integrating green coding material.

Question 2: Which modules from a traditional computer science degree program are suitable for an extension with green coding content? Which modules would you add only for a green coding curriculum?

The experts stated that incorporating green coding content into a traditional computer science degree program should be approached with a broad perspective. They emphasize the necessity of practical measurement in this context, emphasizing that every area within the program is suitable for extension with green coding content. Experts in software engineering emphasize the importance of addressing software design User Experience (UX) to minimize usage time and potentially improve sustainability. They also argue for a complete measuring methodology considering the entire software life cycle, including the production, usage, and disposal phases. Experts have advocated that conventional computer science degree programs should integrate green coding content into their fundamental modules. The speakers emphasized the necessity of effectively integrating green coding concepts into software development, establishing it as an indispensable field component. It has been proposed to modify the Software Engineering module, wherein the credit value would be augmented from 5 to 10 ECTS, with a specific emphasis on sustainability. The module focused on Software Evolution was deemed a highly suitable option for green coding content because of its capacity to serve as a framework for examining the evolution of software systems from the perspective of environmental sustainability. The experts further underscored the significance of considering the university's profile when expanding programs with green coding content. Furthermore, experts advise including mandatory study program introductions to the fundamentals of green coding and mandatory elective modules. They stress that "if you don't know it, don't do it," emphasizing the importance of incorporating green coding information across the curriculum or cutting it whenever possible. Experts emphasize the relevance of practical components in software engineering, highlighting measurement issues and what should be analyzed. They also recommend incorporating lectures on current research subjects, such as Green AI, with activities such as paper reading to gain a more comprehensive understanding of green coding ideas. Databases and Network Technology modules were deemed appropriate for inclusion in the green coding curriculum due to their capacity to function as specialized platforms for examining concepts and practices about data management and network infrastructure within the field of green coding.

Question 3: What practices/technologies stand out most regarding green coding? Are there specific practices/technologies that are particularly suitable for green coding?

Efficiency is a fundamental principle in green coding, which significantly emphasizes optimizing software and processes to minimize resource usage. Metrics play a vital role in assessing the environmental implications of software development, facilitating developers in monitoring their advancement towards achieving green computing targets. Accurate measurements are crucial in green coding, according to experts. This requires a detailed assessment of the code's environmental impact, including measures such as energy usage, resource utilization, and carbon emissions. Developers can acquire valuable insights into the environmental footprint of their code by utilizing extensive measurement procedures.

The researchers further underscore the significance of considering hardware implications in green computing endeavors, commonly known as "Green by IT", which recognizes the interdependence of software and hardware elements and their influence on ecological sustainability. The experts recommend incorporating supplementary sustainability features into green coding procedures, considering environmental and social factors. This is because the technological design has the potential to influence societal requirements and overall welfare. Green coding experts advocate for the use of sustainable design patterns. These coding methodologies and architectural approaches emphasize efficiency, resource management, and environmentally beneficial activities. Developers can improve the overall sustainability of their codebase by adding specific patterns, such as algorithms that decrease computational effort or data structures that optimize memory utilization. A software system's design can either increase or minimize its environmental impact. Well-structured and efficiently designed applications may use fewer computational resources, resulting in lower energy consumption. On the other hand, poorly designed code may strain hardware resources, resulting in increased energy usage and a larger carbon footprint. As a result, experts emphasize the need to create decisions in green coding intentionally approaches that prioritize sustainability.

Question 4: What are possible barriers or challenges that educators might face when trying to integrate green coding into their curriculum, and how can they be addressed? What can go wrong?

The experts explained educators' diverse challenges and potential opportunities when integrating green coding (green coding) into their teaching framework. The presenters placed considerable importance on the need for easily accessible green coding material, the development of a comprehensive curriculum, and effectively communicating the benefits of green coding to colleagues. One acknowledges the challenges in effectively conveying the importance of green coding to colleagues, particularly when they need more understanding or concerns regarding incorporating sustainability principles if they don't directly profit from it.

Question 5: Should the GI, for example, propose the development of a green coding curriculum? If so, how detailed should it be?

The experts agree that the Gesellschaft für Informatik should develop a green coding (green coding) curriculum, drawing upon pre-existing curricula. This methodology guarantees that the instruction provided by green coding is founded on well-established ideas and can be seamlessly incorporated into pre-existing educational frameworks. They additionally propose the development of optimal methodologies for integrating green coding ideas into practical implementations beyond conventional academic environments, hence facilitating wider acceptance across many professional fields. The experts recommend that the GI put out three separate models for developing green coding curriculum advice to accommodate the varied requirements of learners and educational institutions. The proposals put out by the experts offer a comprehensive framework for the participation of the GI in developing a green coding curriculum. These recommendations include utilizing pre-existing curricula, considering learners' varying backgrounds, highlighting the importance of practical application, suggesting multiple models, and ensuring alignment with emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI). To enhance the likelihood of successful adoption, the participants advise using financial resources akin to the AI Campus initiative to empower educational institutions in developing and delivering productive green coding modules.